

SES Instructions and Materials

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RRIZSCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

The present document provides instructions on how to set up and operate the SES. Also, it provides examples of the materials that need to develop beforehand, such as the board and cards.

Before the session begins, the people are asked to undertake a role, describe it and define their long-term objectives. There are four roles: policy-maker, business, civil society organisation and academia (hereinafter referred to as “participants”). Also, there is one observer (hereinafter referred to as “public voice”). A brief description of each role is provided below:

- **Policy-maker.** A key public or political administration actor responsible for decision-making and implementation in the topic being explored (i.e., the domain of interest or the regional dilemma).
- **Business.** The representative of a business with meaningful involvement and/ or stake in the topic under discussion. It can be a large or multinational company with an influential role or a small- to medium-sized business with some local influence.
- **Civil Society Organisation.** The representative of a civil society organisation which undertakes activities influencing decision-making and/ or public opinion.
- **Academia.** The representative of a local university, faculty or laboratory that produces research relevant to the theme and can influence decision-making and/ or public opinion.
- **The Public Voice.** A substantial group of citizens and voters.

In each session, participants explore two contradicting scenarios (e.g., a positive and a negative scenario) during three time horizons in the future (e.g., 2021, 2026, and 2031). The board is divided into two areas, one on the left and one on the right part of the board, each dedicated to one scenario. In each such area, the three semi-circles represent the three time horizons (see Figure 4). Each session includes seven steps.

Step 1 - The session begins with the first scenario at the first time horizon. The moderator introduces participants to the “new world” where they have been placed. In particular, the moderator reads the megatrend cards and one scenario detail card. The **megatrend cards** describe worldwide, long-term trends that apply to both scenarios and all three time horizons. The **scenario detail cards** are six, each containing information on trends and events taking place in a particular time horizon (see Figure 6).

Step 2 – Each participant receives a few **action cards** with examples of actions they can take. They pick a card based on the information provided to them previously and their priorities and place the card on the board in the semi-circle corresponding to the relevant time horizon. Also, each participant has the option to pick a **real-life card** and follow the instructions written there.

Step 3 - At the same time, participants are invited to put **resource tokens** on their action cards. The number of resource tokens available to each participant for all time horizons is provided by the **scenario disk**. Allocating resource tokens to an action card approximates investing in that action and signifies how supportive the participant is of that action.

Figure 1: Example of an SES board

Step 4 – Once all four participants have taken action, the public voice can choose to support or rebel against them. In particular, the public voice holds several **special resource tokens** (see Figure 6), which it attributes to the action cards he/ she likes the most.

Step 5 – After all, the moderator creates a wrap-up story and calculates each participant's **score**. The scores are calculated by multiplying the number of resources allocated to each action card by the number of special tokens attributed to that card by the public voice.

Step 6 – Participants proceed to the second time horizon, where all the above steps repeat. What is different now is that participants can **collaborate**. In particular, participants can place a few of their resource tokens on other participants' cards. In this case, the score of the original owner of the action card is calculated considering the sum of all resource tokens. The score of the other partner is calculated considering only the resource tokens that he/ she invested in that card. The third time horizon takes place in a manner identical to the second time horizon.

Step 7 - At the end, the moderator summarises what happened under the first scenario and calculates the final scores. Also, the moderator asks participants to assess how well they have reached their long-term objectives and how close the participants' actions have brought them to a sustainable future. Finally, all the above steps repeat for the second scenario.

The whole session usually takes about 3 to 4 hours to complete. Figure 5 shows how the board would look after completing the first scenario. Also, Figure 6 shows several of the material required. The SES depends heavily on the scenarios used. Thus, any materials from previous SES, such as scenario detail cards, can not be used as-is. The team needs to devote time and resources to adapting the SES to the region's specificities and the scenarios' content.

Figure 2: Example of how the board would look after completing the first scenario

Figure 3: SES material, including (1) a scenario detail card; (2) a megatrend card; (3) an action card; (4) a scenario disk; (5) a real-life card; (6) a special resource token; and (7) a resource token.

In addition, RRI2SCALE created a shorter version of the SES, without tokens and shorter time horizons. The board is provided below. It can be used when participants have less than 3-4 hours available.

RRI2Scale | Scenario Exploration System (SES)

Figure 4: Example of the shorter SES board